

Relative Implications of Human Rights Institutions in India

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Abstract

Human rights, as the inherent birth rights of every individual, are entitled to be enjoyed by every human being. Ever since the establishment of United Nations Organization in 1945, human rights has occupied a centre-stage of global community and subsequently, the adoption of international bill of human rights in the post-1948 has also brought a paradigm shift, specially in the context of legal status and position of individual under the international law and its system that has, eventually allowed to change the traditional equation between the sovereign state and its subjects as well. The article aims to explore the global as well as national responsibilities for promotion and protection of human rights of individuals elsewhere in the world. It further focuses on relative implications of global initiatives for establishment of national human rights institutions and also analyses the relative outcome of national and state rights commissions in India.

Key words

Natural rights, jurisprudence, constitutional mandate, liberal democracy, humanitarian regime, customary international law, institutional autonomy, municipal law and democratic governance

Introduction

Human rights are entitled to be enjoyed by everyone being born in human society irrespective of all differences among the individuals. As such, naturalist philosophers believe that human rights are nothing but the natural rights of individual which can't either be created or taken away by any authority including the state. However, on the contrary, it can be seen that the very notion of human rights seems to have recognized the state as the sole guarantor, promoter and protector of human rights of its subjects rather than a mere source of such intrinsic rights. In a way, human history also reveals countless number of people struggles for emancipation of their basic rights and freedoms against their tyrannical rulers and systems elsewhere in the world, and eventually such historical events have led to transform the concept of natural rights into the status of enforceable human rights of individuals. In this regard, it can be noted that the emerging jurisprudence of contemporary global human rights and humanitarian regime with reference to the international status and position of individuals, more particularly in the post-UN, has postulated a paradigm shift in the area of international relations, and eventually, nation members are being obligated to assimilate the international standard setting norms of human rights into their respective domestic legal frameworks. The same has also been adequately reflected into the Constitution of India under the banner of fundamental rights and directive principles of state policy. Undoubtedly, such a constitutional mandate has created a unique premise in developing a new national human rights jurisprudence as well. Nevertheless, the important role of constitutional bodies, statutory commissions, public defenders, ombudsmen

and other related institutions are equally worth mentioning especially in promoting and protecting of human rights in India.

Global mandates and human rights

Many thinkers and legal philosophers have defined the term human rights from different perspectives. However, the very adoption of the Charter of UN in 1945 uses the term “human rights” in different parts of Charter as one of the means to realize the objectives of the global organization, that has revealed the significant values of human rights at the global level as well. Eventually, inclusion of such human rights provisions in the world constitution has also marked a remarkable global initiative for promotion and protection of human rights across the globe. Though the term “human rights” is neither defined nor enumerated in any provision of the Charter, the UN and its member states are obligated under the Charter to further evolve and develop human rights jurisprudence. The UN General Assembly, as a part of its mandate under the Charter, adopted the international bill of human rights in the post-second world war. One of the objectives for adoption of the international bill of human rights was not only to set forth a universally accepted standard norms of human rights for all the nations and all the people but also to establish global bodies for monitoring human rights situation around the world. In addition, the Charter-based UN human rights bodies and other treaty-based bodies have also been put in place for monitoring the implementation and enforcement of human rights by the national government in their respective jurisdictions. However, the past global experiences virtually reveal adequate testimonies of national governments being concerned as the main actors for the cause of human rights violation of individuals elsewhere, and on the top, those victims of human rights violation belong to sovereign state as well. It is also pertinent that responsible national government often violates human rights of its own citizens in the name of welfare governance, unity, integrity, maintenance of law and order etc. Whereas on the other hand, judiciary and other concerned governmental agencies are not in the position to cope up the emerging issue and challenges of human rights efficiently due to multifarious factors and reasons. As such, there is an apprehension developed in the mind of general public losing the notion of trust and belief towards the stakeholders of a democratic governance. Henceforth, establishment of national human rights institutions has undoubtedly become a need of the day in combating with the emerging challenges of human rights.

It is also pertinent to mention that even before the adoption of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights in 1948 by the UN General Assembly, the Economic, Social and Council (ECOSOC), which is one of the major organs of UN, urged the member states to set up the national commission on human rights in their respective regions. In this regard, the ECOSOC also took the resolution recognizing the role of national human rights institutions which could play vital role in promoting and protecting human rights in the regions; as such, the UN and its subsidiary agencies began to roll out their initiatives significantly in dealing with human rights issues from 1980s. It is worth mentioning that the UN Secretary General was given the specific assignment to materialize the UN initiatives on human rights. The World Conference on Human Rights held in Vienna in 1993 urged the national governments to strengthen national institutions for promotion and protection of human rights of individuals. The adoption of the Paris Principles in 1993 lays down the essential characteristics for setting up the National Human Rights Institutions (NHRIs). Accordingly, most of the national governments have indeed created a global benchmark by

setting up human institutions in their respective region. One of the purposes for the establishment of NHRIs is to bridge the gap between the government and general public. In a way, the Paris Principles is the sole foundation of NHRIs that lays down a minimum standard for their organizations, structures, powers and functions, among others. It lays down six guidelines; viz i) Broad mandate ii) Autonomy iii) Independence iv) Pluralism v) Adequate resources and vi) Adequate investigation power. These are the minimum guidelines to be followed by the NHRIs for their effective functions.

As a matter of fact, the role of UN Centre of Human Rights and UN Commission on Human Rights are also equally significance in making realized the objectives of the Paris Principles. Installation of a number of national human rights institutions in the post-1993 elsewhere in the world as per the yardsticks of the Paris Principles has been one of the glaring testimonies of relative significance of positive measures undertaken by the UN and its members. In fact, such national and regional human rights institutions were also set up in conformity with the international human rights standards as set forth in the international bill of human rights. In addition, the Global Alliance for NHRIs (GANHRI), which was earlier known as the International Coordinating Committee of NHRIs, has also been playing an important role in facilitating the promotion and protection of human rights around the globe as an important network of all the NHRIs set up elsewhere in the world. It not only aims to coordinate and support the functions of NHRIs but also virtually engages with the UN Human Rights Council and also with other treaty-based human rights monitoring bodies. The GANHRI has an imperative obligation to grant the accreditation to the NHRIs as per the fulfillment of the Paris Principles and the same is to be reviewed once in five years so as to examine the compliance of the said principles.

Human rights and Indian judiciary

Indian legal system follows the rule of law that emanates from international law where law by itself is not considered to be an expression of justice. It is also true that law either be domestic or international law shall be meaningless unless it is implemented and enforced by the competent enforcement agencies. The constitutional scheme, as mandated in Article 51 © of the Constitution obligates the state to strive and promote international law in India. International conventions and treaties are not the self-executing documents in India; therefore, the parliament of India under Article 253 of the Constitution is empowered to enact appropriate domestic laws in order to give effect to international laws and treaties in India. On other hand, the constitutional courts in the commonwealth countries like in India, they are empowered to interpret the domestic laws by relying on the provisions of the Charter of UN and also other relevant provisions of the International human rights instruments to which India has been a high contracting party. As such, the courts in India interpret the text of the Constitution liberally by referring to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights *inter alia* the other relevant global human rights treaties when deciding the cases of human rights violations. For instance, the Supreme Court of India held in *People's Union for Civil Liberties vs. Union of India*. (1972)3 SCC 433) that the rules of customary international law, which are not found contrary to the municipal law of India, shall be deemed to be incorporated in the domestic law. In *Kesavananda Bharti vs. State of Kerala* (AIR 1973 SC 1461), the apex court also held that this court must interpret Article 51 of the Constitution in the light of the UN Charter as well as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. The same court in the *Jolly George Varghese vs. Bank of Cochin*, (AIR 1980 SC 474) held that the Declaration has not

created a binding set of rules; however, international binding treaties have stimulated and informed the national judicial institutions and also inspired the national legislative actions. Similarly, in *Kishorchand vs. State of Himachal Pradesh*, (1991 SCJ 68), the same court held that the Declaration has the great influence in the interpretation of the Constitution of India. Therefore, it is clear that the juridical approach towards the promotion and protection of human rights in India has shown its pro-active approach towards the evolution of a new human rights Jurisprudence within the domestic legal framework in matching with the universally accepted standard and norms set forth in the international bill of human rights.

Indian judiciary has interpreted the text of the Constitution liberally by referring to the international documents as the sources of inspiration, especially in the context of human rights. It can also be noted that the pro-active interpretation of domestic laws by Indian judiciary has evolved a new human rights jurisprudence which has also inspired the human rights institutions in this country. In a way, the constitutional courts uphold the rule of law and they are also vested with the power to restrain the executive wing of the state from exercising absolute and arbitrary powers. Simply because they are supposed to act as the final interpreter, guarantor, protector and guardian of fundamental rights of individuals. Henceforth, excessive or illegal actions of the state agencies are not only counter-checked and balanced by the judiciary but also made them accountable for their wrong actions. Human rights of individuals are protected and secured by the court, and tyranny of the government actions is being contained by the court vigilance as well. On the contrary, though judiciary has acted as the fearless watch-dog of human rights and fundamental freedoms by upholding the values of liberal democracy, the judicial process, adopted in India, is dilatory, expensive and technical in its proceedings. Besides the courts are being overburdened with thousands of cases pending; therefore, the judiciary can't alone handle with the demands of human rights justice. It is pertinent that issues of human rights violations cannot be addressed by the judiciary alone due to many profound reasons. One of such reasons may be its procedural cumbersome which normally make hardship for the victims of human rights violation to reach out the court and get the appropriate remedy within a period of time. It seems that the prevailing judicial process also facilitates the maxim "justice delayed is justice denied" especially for the victims of human rights violations. As such, the national human rights institutions have become relevant in the contemporary India because their unique organizational structures, positions, powers and functions among others. Both the constitutional bodies and statutory commissions, set up with their specific mandates by the responsible governments, shall be independent watchdog of human rights of individuals, and they have become the appropriate mechanisms for promotion and protection of human rights in India. However, it is to be noted that the establishment of national human rights institutions neither aims to replace the judiciary nor to function as the parallel body of court but they are supplementary and complementary to each other.

In a way, the NHRIs are the extra-ordinary human rights bodies which are unique in their nature and also found different from court, legislature, executive and non-governmental organization. There are three imperative tasks to be carried out by such hybrid institutions for realizing a meaningful promotion and protection of human rights in the country; viz, i) they can advise the government of the day ii) they can make awareness to the people iii) they can handle human complaints and also investigate. Such unique features of the NHRIs can cover a wide range of scope for striving new changes in the society and also create a good human rights culture. They

are also competent, impartial and independent investigating bodies which are free from the government intervention. Nevertheless, the national human rights protection system circumscribes to create a conducive atmosphere where the NHRIs can function independently since they can represent the silence voices of human rights victims. They can handle human rights complaints and conduct free and fair investigation into the matters as a civil court. The NHRIs not only occupy a place between the government and civil society but they can also bridge the gap between the two; therefore, they can make the government accountable for its actions and they can also educate and sensitize the general public unlike the government agencies. They keep monitoring human rights situation and report their findings, views and recommendations to the concerned authorities and responsible government as well. As such, establishment of human rights commissions both at the national and regional levels across the world has not only facilitated in transforming the international human rights standards into practical reality but also immensely supported in exploring the indigenous local flavour without compromising the essence of both the characters.

Human rights institutions

It is a universal phenomenon that Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) working in the field of human rights, as being the watch-dog of government, keep criticizing the responsible governments whenever and wherever the issue of human rights violations occur. In this regard, republic of India is not an exception to such situation since the union of India has been a high contracting state party to many international human rights treaties, and she has the both the moral and legal obligation to address the violations of human rights in compliance with the global standards. In addition, constant demand from inside and outside of India for setting up independent fact-finding human rights bodies for conducting impartial investigation into alleged violations of human rights was one of the profound reasons for establishing the national and state human rights commissions. As a matter of fact, republic of India was also in need of self-regulating and self-vigilance national human rights bodies of its own and henceforth, the Protection of Human Rights Ordinance was promulgated in 1993 by the government of India and subsequently, the same was replaced by the enactment of the Protection of Human Rights Act, 1993. The Act provides for establishment of a National Human Rights Commission at the centre, the State Human Rights Commissions at state level and the Human Rights Courts at the district of the state. Accordingly, the National Rights Commission was set up to promote and protect human rights of citizens and individuals at the centre. In the similar manner, several State Human Rights Commissions and the Human Rights Courts at the districts level were also established across the country. Such rights bodies play a pivotal role in implementing provisions of human rights embodied in the international documents as well as in the national legislation and they are considered to be the safety valves of parliamentary democracy as well. Since their powers are intended to be so wide even to oversee the functioning of the state agencies, the general public have often considered them as the significant watchdog of democratic governance.

The role of civil organizations and citizens' forums, more particularly those NGOs working in the field of human rights are worth mentioning their remarkable contributions to the establishment of national and state human rights institutions in India. Since the rights Commission can act as a fact-finding body as well as a competent civil court, it can also take cases of human rights violation *suo moto* or on complaint filed by the victim or others: therefore, the Commissions aim to serve

as a redressal mechanism for human rights in the region and also fill the loophole found in prevailing the legal system. On other hand, human rights institutions are primarily designed to hear and investigate individual charges of human rights violations according to the existing laws and procedures. It is pertinent to say that such human rights institutions are being set up by the responsible governments with a view to ensuring effective realization of its constitutional objectives. The institutional autonomy relating to their status, position, mode of appointment, services, salaries and allowances of the chairmen and members of the Commission are constitutionally secured so as to enable them to function independently and impartially in exercising their statutory functions and powers under the 1993 Act. The Act authorizes the Commissions to exercise the powers of a civil court under the Code of Civil Procedure and it also virtually provides some procedures to be followed while dealing with the armed forces personnel involved with violations of human rights as well. The core objectives for establishment of both the National and State Human Rights Commissions are not only to promote, protect human rights of individuals but also to disseminate culture of human rights and culture of legalism among the people. Most importantly, they keep facilitating the government machinery while discharging its constitutional obligations in retaining a good governance.

The rights commissions are impartial, independent fact-finding statutory bodies which are unique in their nature of functioning in the field of human rights. It can intervene in the court proceedings and also assess human rights conditions by visiting jails, rehabilitation centers and homes among others. It undertakes sensitization programme by working together with the human rights NGOs and also submit its annual as well as special reports to governments along with its views and recommendations. Though the state rights bodies are not subordinate to the national rights commission, the actual motto of the state human rights commission is to supplement and compliment the working of the NHRC but not to replace it.

Conclusion

Issue of human rights has always been the global concerned since the very inception of international organization and interestingly, the global community focus has also been shifted literally from the adoption of international human rights treaties to the establishment of national human rights institutions. It turns to be a universal phenomenon which has been widely adopted because of its meaningful implications derived from the Paris Principles and also from the significant contributions of NHRIs activities elsewhere in the world. The Paris Principles not only facilitates the NHRIs as the connecting link between the governments and general public but also enables to serve as the important basis and foundation for keeping a constant engagement between the NHRIs and the global human rights bodies. Human rights commission is literally different from the court, tribunal, legislature, executive and NGOs almost in all respects. It has varieties of statutory functions and powers as set forth in the relevant legislation. It can not only act as a competent quasi-judicial body but also sensitize significantly the general masses about human rights culture and values. In addition, the measures for protection of human rights undertaken by the responsible government of the day can also be used as a common yardstick for evaluating the quality of governance of a welfare state *vis a vis* the equation between the legitimate government and general public. In a way, respect and observance of global human rights standards by all the nations and all the people is being considered as a universally accepted currency of international relations. Therefore, it is imperative for both the NHRIs and

responsible governments to obtain their legitimacy and earn their respect from the general public and international community as well.

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